

Significance of Value Education in the Context of NEP 2020

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ABSTRACT

Value is the most important part of human being. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasises the importance of value education in developing students' academic talents as well as their moral, ethical, and social responsibility. The purpose of the study is to explain the various strategies of value education recommended by NEP 2020 and to understand the significance of value education in NEP 2020. The present study is qualitative in nature, and, specifically, it is a documentary-based study. This study is mainly based on primary and secondary data collected from National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 reports and various highly reputed journals, articles, books, e-books, and websites. NEP 2020 aims to promote holistic development by integrating principles like empathy, honesty, and social responsibility throughout academic fields. This paper aims to focus on the various factors, strategies, and significance that play a vital role in value education as recommended by NEP 2020. The study concludes that value education is fundamental to the objectives of NEP 2020, striving to cultivate a progressive, ethical, and diverse society, preparing students for both careers and purposeful, responsible lives.

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INTRODUCTION

Education is not just about gaining knowledge and abilities; it is also about establishing moral values, ethics, and a feeling of accountability. In this regard, value education is critical in developing persons

who are not just intellectually capable but also socially and emotionally responsible. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 acknowledges the significance of value-based education in developing character, empathy, respect for others, and a dedication to social justice and environmental sustainability. The aim of education is the all-round development of the personality of an individual, which includes physical, mental, social, intellectual, moral, and spiritual development (Chakma & Dvivedi, 1986). The NEP 2020 aspires to improve India's education system by incorporating ethical and human values into the curriculum in order to develop well-rounded, conscientious, and responsible citizens. The strategy emphasises the importance of holistic education, in which students are not only taught academic subjects but also encouraged to cultivate values like integrity, compassion, honesty, and patriotism. With an emphasis on Indian culture, traditions, and universal human values, NEP 2020 aims to create in students a strong sense of national pride, respect for diversity, and global responsibility.

Value

The German philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche used the word 'values' in 1880. Until then, the term value was employed as a verb meaning to value something or as a singular noun meaning the measure of anything, such as the value of money, food, or labor (Sharma & Singh, 2024). Nietzsche used the word 'values' in the plural to denote moral attitudes and beliefs that were subjective and personal (Ravi, 2018). Values are personal aspirations (Hussain, 2023). Values are ideas, fundamental beliefs, and aspirations that serve as overarching guidelines for behaviour and reference points for decision-making (Parankimalil, 2015). Values are fundamental for individuals to achieve a fulfilling and productive life (Azmi & Naidu, 2024).

VALUE EDUCATION

Value education is the process of instilling moral, ethical and social ideals in persons. It goes beyond typical academic learning by emphasizing character development and accountability. Value education is the study of values for both personal enjoyment and the good of society (Ravi, 2018). It seeks to provide people with the ability to discriminate between good and evil and make ethical decisions. It is based on values. Value education is the process of determining principles such as honesty, integrity, and fairness. According to National Education Policy (NEP) 2020- "Value-based education will include the development of humanistic, ethical, constitutional, universal human values of truth (satya), righteous conduct (dharma), peace (shanti), love (prem), nonviolence (ahimsa), scientific temper, citizenship values, and also life-skills; lessons in seva/service and participation in community service programmes

will be considered an integral part of a holistic education” (NEP 2020, 11.8, p.37). Here some core values are arranged in a cycle.

Fig 1: Value Education cycle

According to **John Dewey (1966)**, “Value education means primarily to prize to esteem to appraise, holding it dear and also the act of passing judgment upon the nature and amount of its value as compared with something else”.

“The purpose of the education system is to develop good human beings capable of rational thought and action, possessing compassion and empathy, courage and resilience, scientific temper and creative imagination, with sound ethical moorings and values.” – **National Education Policy 2020**

Classification of values

Swami Vivekananda’s Classification of Values

Swamiji classified six categories of values-

- | | |
|-------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| 1. Cultivation of heart | 4. Personal purity and social purity |
| 2. Fearlessness | 5. Self-sacrifice |
| 3. Non-injury | 6. Service to others |

Mahatma Gandhi's Classification of Values

1. Ahimsa (Non-violence)
2. Satya (Truth)
3. Astayans (Non-thriving)
4. Brahmacharya (Purity)
5. Aparigraha (Non-acquisitiveness)
6. Sharirshram (Physical work)
7. Aswada (control of palate)
8. Sarvatra Bhavjavarjana (Fearlessness)
9. Sarva Dharma Sambhava (Looking up at all religions equally toleration)
10. Swadeshi (Patriotism)
11. Sparsha Bhavana (Abolition of untouchability)

General classification of Value Education

- 1. Personal values education:** Personal values are the fundamental beliefs and concepts that direct an individual's actions, choices, and overall perception of significance of life. It fosters constructive cognitive processes and habits, which is advantageous for their personal development (Shah, 2023). Personal values are honesty, self-motivation, excellence, self-confidence, punctuality, cleanliness, and consistency etc.
- 2. Social values education:** Social values are the principles and ideologies, that help us to interact with each other. Some social values are respect of elders, justice, equality, freedom, responsibility, forgiveness, social service and protection of culture etc. One of the primary purposes of social value education is to prepare students to be decent citizens who contribute positively to society (Shah, 2023)
- 3. Moral values education:** Moral values are the principles that instruct people on how to discriminate between right and wrong. Good conduct, sympathy, empathy, honesty, kindness etc these values also called character values.
- 4. Spiritual values education:** Spiritual values are the fundamental ideas that shape a person's sense of purpose, meaning and connection to something greater than themselves. They have a significant impact on ethical behaviour, relationships, and personal development. Some common spiritual values are self-discipline, devotion to God, inner peace, purity, and faith etc.
- 5. Educational values education:** Educational values refer to the principles and beliefs that guide and shape the purpose and practice of education. They go beyond simply imparting knowledge and skills, focusing on the development of well-rounded individuals and responsible citizens. Educational values

are academic excellence, critical thinking, creativity and innovation, respect for diversity, collaboration and teamwork etc.

Objectives of the Study

1. To explain the various strategies of value education recommended by NEP 2020.
2. To understand the significance of value education in NEP 2020.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This is a documentary-based study and qualitative research in nature. In this study, primary data is collected from National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 reports, and secondary data is collected from various sources of information such as books, e-books, high-reputed journals, articles, websites, reports and newspapers, etc.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Objective-1: To explain the various strategies of value education recommended by NEP 2020.

National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 directs the NCERT to identify the required values and skills and includes mechanisms for their transaction in the National Curriculum Framework for early childhood and school education (*NEP 2020, 4.4, p.12*). Here are the various strategies of value education, recommended by NEP 2020 which are as follows:

1. National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 has recommended various indoor and outdoor games, puzzles, dramas, poem, stories, music, and drawings in the curriculum at the Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) level of education for inculcating desirable values among children (Chakma & Dvivedi, 1986).
2. It suggests the seamless integration of value education into all topics, rather than considering it as a distinct subject. This entails integrating ethical and moral concepts into mathematics, physics, social science, and other fields. The curriculum should incorporate content that promotes human and constitutional values, including empathy, respect, compassion, and democratic principles.
3. Training in drawing, painting, and dancing should be organised to foster aesthetic values.
4. Group activities such as cleaning the campus of the school, visiting slums, service camps, hospital visits, and visits to diverse faith-based places of worship should be included in the value education curriculum.
5. According to NEP 2020, classroom activities, debates, and readings should focus on promoting ethical and moral reasoning among pupils. Languages, literature, and social science courses might indirectly convey ethical and moral values.

Objective -2: To understand the significance of value education in NEP 2020.

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasises the value education as an essential component of the educational system. In this context, value education refers to the transmission of ethical and moral values that form students' personalities, contribute to their overall development, and prepare them to make meaningful contributions to society. Here is why value education is significant in the context of NEP 2020:

- 1. Holistic Development:** The NEP 2020 seeks to go beyond academic knowledge and focus on the development of vital life skills, creativity, and character. Value education is a critical component of this viewpoint. It ensures students not only perform academically but also develop values such as empathy, respect, integrity, and accountability.
- 2. Building Responsible Citizens:** The policy emphasises the importance of education in training students to be responsible, active, and knowledgeable citizens of the country. Value education teaches students about their social, ethical, and cultural responsibilities. It helps people to contribute significantly to society and make decisions based on sound ethical beliefs.
- 3. Promoting Inclusivity and Respect for Diversity:** In a diverse country like India, where learners come from different kinds of cultural, linguistic, and socioeconomic backgrounds, the NEP 2020 emphasises the need for cultivating respect and empathy for all. Value education encourages knowledge and respect for diversity, as well as tolerance and acceptance for different viewpoints, all of which are essential for peaceful coexistence.
- 4. Focus on Emotional and Social Learning:** NEP 2020 integrates emotional and social learning as a key component of education. Value education is critical in this regard since it addresses emotional intelligence, social interactions, conflict resolution, and stress management skills. These aspects of learning help a student's emotional well-being and foster strong interpersonal interactions.
- 5. Ethics in Technology and Innovation:** NEP 2020 emphasises the need for ethics in digital learning. Value education promotes students utilising technology in a responsible, ethical, and accountable manner, which is critical as they navigate an increasingly digital environment.

Conclusion

Value education is an important component of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, which aspires to develop well-rounded persons with strong moral, ethical, and social responsibilities. NEP 2020 proposes an education system that fosters responsible citizens by incorporating values like empathy, integrity, respect, and environmental awareness into the curriculum. It emphasises holistic learning,

combining traditional wisdom with current understanding to produce individuals who make constructive contributions to society. Value education is at the heart of NEP 2020, and it will teach students how to recognise and act ethically in complicated situations. Finally, value education in NEP 2020 promotes a progressive, inclusive, and ethical India by training students not only for vocations but also for life as compassionate and responsible citizens.

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